

THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES: IN-SITU CONSOLIDATION OR IN-SITU WELDING?

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1 Introduction

Processing of thermoplastic composites, using Automated Tape Placement (ATP), is a viable alternative for many applications [1-3]. ATP is a continuous welding process involving heating of the opposite sides of the incoming tape and substrate, pressing them together to promote matrix diffusion across the interlaminar interface and cooling them to allow solidification of the molten matrix. The process has been used by aerospace companies for more than two decades with varying degrees of success. Recent material and technological advancements offer a good opportunity to further enhance the process efficiency and effectiveness. In this paper, we first briefly review the existing process technology. The aim is to highlight the significant influence of the laser heat source on process physics, when all the other process parameters, including the amount of heat input, are kept identical. We also report our recent efforts to model the process numerically and characterise it experimentally. The main conclusion from this study is that appropriate thermal design of the process is key to achieving significant improvements in mechanical properties of final parts.

2 Welding vs. In-Situ Consolidation

Welding of thermoplastics is a manufacturing process for joining two different polymer parts or layers by fusion and consolidation of the interface [4]. As the interlaminar interface is the main process zone, the thermal energy necessary for the process is aimed to be limited to this zone only. A variety of methods are used to supply the necessary thermal energy. Consolidation involves establishment of intimate contact between opposite surfaces of two different parts or plies (intimate contact),

intermolecular diffusion of polymer chains across the interlaminar interface (healing) and void removal or minimisation. The weld joint efficiency is defined as the ratio of the mechanical properties of the weld zone material to the bulk material and is preferred to approach unity, giving visually unseparable plies [3, 5].

In autoclave processing, uniform application of thermal and pressure cycles to the bulk of the material over longer time periods facilitates uniform void reduction through void bubbling, void migration, void coalescing and void collapse mechanisms, leading to the highest level of consolidation (i.e. visually, structurally and morphologically inseparable layers) and highest achievable mechanical properties. In contrast, in most of the welding processes, small weld zone size limits void reduction, while different processing conditions for the bulk tape material and weld zone lead to differences in their properties. Both of these factors lead to lower mechanical properties of welded parts. This shortfall in the properties of the welded parts has led researchers to modify the process to achieve in-situ consolidation of multiple layers rather than just the interface, e.g. Tierney *et al.* have reported that multiple consolidation cycles lead to better consolidation of the entire part and hence, better mechanical properties [6]. This requires larger weld pool size and controlled heating and cooling rates to increase the available time period for various mechanisms. Furthermore, consolidation pressure needs to be applied for prolonged time periods to prevent deconsolidation. Some rearrangement of fibre network is also possible with in-situ consolidation [5]. It has been suggested that many of the newly developed tapes,

having much better quality in terms of void fraction and surface roughness, only need interfacial consolidation and offer further possible gains in process speed and efficiency. However, it is important to note that most of the old as well as new tape materials have maximum crystallinity level of 15% and any further increase in crystallinity levels will require either autoclave or in-situ consolidation.

3 Laser ATP process

Many different thermal sources such as open flame, hot gas, hot shoe, laser, infrared radiation etc., have been used in ATP [7]. Of these, hot gas is the most popular heat source and has been investigated in great detail, both numerically and experimentally [3, 8]. The main drawbacks of the process are poor thermal efficiency, poor dynamic control over the thermal energy input and lower process speed [7]. The potential for employing laser heat input in the tape placement process was recognised early on and has been investigated by a number of researchers [1, 2]. The narrowly focused laser beam allows optimum heat input to a localised area, while offering faster dynamic control.

At the Irish Centre for Composites Research (IComp), a laser ATP machine has just been installed for research on thermoplastic composite tape placement with in-situ consolidation. The machine has a diode laser with 3 kW power, and laser wavelength around 800-900 nm, giving more than 99% energy absorption by the carbon fibres. The surrounding matrix then indirectly heats up to melt. The laser beam is spread through optics to give a range of spot sizes depending upon the distance between the lens and the nip point. The spot size varies between 14x26 mm to 28x50 mm, i.e. the machine can process tape widths between 12.5 mm and 25 mm. Active cooling of the laser optics maintains various components at the working temperature. The stainless steel (SS) consolidation roller, 80 mm in diameter, is hollow from inside to facilitate active cooling. It is supported by a pneumatic cylinder, which allows application of the required consolidation pressure.

4 Numerical Model

The personal safety hazard due to high intensity laser and high temperatures leads to inaccessibility

of the part during laser ATP processing. Thus, numerical simulations could prove useful in enhancing the understanding of the process physics. The thermal modelling of the laser ATP process has been done using COMSOL Multiphysics®. The model uses a quasi-steady assumption since, under constant boundary conditions, the temperature distribution near the nip point can be expected to remain steady [1, 2]. The geometric model for the governing equation [Eq. 1], comprising the hollow SS roller, a portion of the incoming tape and substrate and a portion of the substrate down from the nip point, is shown in Fig. 1. The substrate is assumed to 1.9 mm thick (approx. 13 layers), while the incoming tape is 0.14 mm thick. Table 1 lists the material properties and process parameter values used in the simulations. The substrate is at the mandrel temperature, while the incoming tape is at room temperature. Radiative boundary conditions are imposed on the substrate top surface. In addition, heat loss through convection is modelled for the top surface of the substrate. Energy input via laser irradiation is modelled as boundary heat input for a portion of the incoming tape and the substrate. The substrate bottom surface is maintained at the mandrel temperature, while a constant temperature boundary condition is maintained at the roller outer surface. Two different process speeds were used: 0.01 and 0.1 m/s. Equal heating was assumed for the tape and the substrate.

$$\rho C_p u_{trans} \cdot \nabla T = \nabla \cdot (k \nabla T) + Q \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1 Geometric domain showing the consolidation roller, incoming tape and the substrate for the ATP thermal model.

Table 1 Material properties and process parameters for the Laser ATP thermal model [8]

Material Properties		
K_c [W/(m K)]	[34, 0.34, 0.34]	Thermal conductivity (composite)
ρ_c [Kg/m ³]	1584	Density (Composite)
C_{pc} [J/(Kg K)]	1370	Heat capacity at constant pressure (composite)
K_r [W/(m K)]	44.5	Thermal conductivity (SS Roller)
ρ_r [kg/m ³]	7850	Density (SS roller)
C_{pr} [J/Kg K]	475	Heat capacity at constant pressure (SS roller)

Process Parameters		
T_a [K]	300	Ambient temperature
T_{ml} [K]	553	Mandrel temperature
T_r [K]	473	Roller temperature
T_g [K]	416	PEEK glass transition temperature
T_m [K]	607	PEEK melting temperature
h_a [W/(m ² K)]	13	Heat transfer coefficient
ε [1]	0.9	Emissivity

Figure 2 shows the temperature distribution for different process speeds. It is clear that:

- (i) The size of the molten zone depends on the time available for heat conduction in the through-thickness direction; at high speeds, the laser is able to heat only a very thin surface layer of material. A temperature difference of around 50 °C exists across the incoming tape thickness. Beyeler and Guceru [1] and Grove [2] report similar results, in a system irradiated by a laser beam with similar energy density.
- (ii) The maximum temperature in the material varies with process speed. In many cases, it can even be lower than the melting temperature of the polymer (the maximum temperature values are 404 and 312 °C for process speeds of 0.01 and 0.1 m/s, respectively). This would lead to poor

consolidation, and hence, poor mechanical properties of the final part.

(a) Process speed: 0.01 m/s

(b) Process speed: 0.1 m/s

Fig. 2 Temperature distribution in the laser ATP process (a) process speed: 0.01 m/s, and (b) process speed: 0.1 m/s.

5 Experimental Validation

As real-time monitoring of the ATP process is challenging, an easier and straightforward option is to characterise the prepreg raw tape as well as processed laminates. A carbon-fibre/PEEK thermoplastic material (T 60% IM7 / PEEK-150) from Suprem [9] was used in this study. Tapes with two different widths, 12 mm and 150 mm, were purchased. Wide tape laminates were hand laid-up and processed using an in-house autoclave [Fig. 3]. The ATP laminates were manufactured by the machine supplier, AFPT at their German facility. The processing speed was 10 m/min. Table 2 lists the tests used for tape and laminate materials characterisation, while various mechanical properties were characterised using the Interlaminar Shear Strength (ILSS), Flexure and Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) tests. In general, the incoming tape had less than 1% void content, 60% fibre volume fraction and ~10% crystallinity. Samples for various tests were extracted from the autoclaved laminates using a diamond cutter, while the ATP-made samples were extracted by a water-jet cutting machine.

Fig. 3 Autoclave temperature and pressure cycles to manufacture laminates.

Table 2 Tape and laminate material properties characterised by respective analysis technique

Material Property	Analysis Technique
Void Content	Microscopy/Image Analysis
Fibre Volume Fraction	Microscopy/Image Analysis
% Crystallinity	DSC

ILSS tests were performed on specimens extracted from both autoclave and ATP manufactured laminates in accordance with BS EN 2563:1997. A minimum of five tests were performed for each manufacturing process. Nominal specimen dimensions were 20 mm x 10 mm x 2 mm with $[0]_{16}$ layup. The span and nose radii were 10 mm and 3 mm, respectively. Figure 4 shows a representative load-displacement chart from one of the tests. The peak load was recorded for each test and the apparent ILSS was calculated. The autoclave laminate samples exhibited 30% higher strength than ATP laminate samples (Table 3).

Fig. 4 Representative Load – crosshead displacement chart for the ILSS test.

For flexural testing, a minimum of five tests were performed for each manufacturing process. Nominal specimen dimensions were 100 mm x 10 mm x 2 mm with $[0]_{16}$ layup and the span was 80 mm in accordance with BS EN 2562:1997. Figure 5 shows a representative load-displacement chart from one of the tests. The autoclaved samples exhibited approximately 10% higher modulus and 30% higher strength compared to ATP samples (Table 3).

Fig. 5 Representative Load-Cross head stroke chart for the Flexural test.

Table 3 Comparison of Interlaminar Shear Strength (ILSS), flexural modulus and strength and fracture toughness properties of autoclaved and ATP laminates.

	Autoclave	ATP
ILSS (MPa)	112	78
Flexural Modulus (MPa)	1775	1207
Flexural Strength (MPa)	141	124
DCB (Initiate/Arrest) (kJ/m ²)	1.32/0.92	2.15/1.67

Three DCB specimens were tested for both the autoclave and ATP processes. The nominal dimensions of the DCB specimens were 150 mm x 25 mm x 4 mm with [0]₃₀ lay-up. The cross-head stroke rate used was 3 mm/min. Crack length was measured using a digital imaging data acquisition system, which also acquired the load and extension (δ) signals. In general, the DCB specimens from both the processes exhibited unstable or “stick-slip” crack propagation (Figure 6). Crack growth was in short bursts with periods of crack arrest and short periods of stable propagation. Mode I fracture toughness was determined using standard beam theory analysis method. The flexural modulus determined from the flexural tests was used in the analysis. ATP laminates were found to be significantly tougher than autoclaved laminates. DSC analysis of autoclave laminates revealed significantly higher crystallinity levels (above 30%)

relative to ATP laminates (16.5%), which correlates with the above findings. This is also in agreement with the small weld zone size predicted by the thermal model, which limits the consolidation as well as increase in crystallinity level.

Fig. 6 Representative load-displacement chart for the DCB test showing stick-slip crack propagation.

6 Process Modifications

Numerical simulations and experimental results in the preceding sections suggest that the existing ATP process struggles to achieve optimal bulk material properties, particularly those that depend on a high level of crystallinity. Further work is planned to see if varying process parameters, particularly laser parameters can improve this. However, it seems that to achieve better properties, the process may need to be modified to better control the heating and cooling rates. Preheating has been proposed to lead to better consolidation [1]. In addition, the roller temperature is understood to have significant influence on the temperature gradients in the incoming tape and on the weld pool size. To investigate possible modifications, the roller and mandrel temperatures in the thermal model were increased to 300 °C. Note that adhesion of the molten polymer to the SS roller is a known issue. However, by judiciously selecting a suitable roller material, the problem of molten polymer sticking to the roller surface can be reduced. In addition, pre-heating of the incoming substrate was simulated using an additional heat input of 540 watts over 0.03m length.

Fig. 7 Temperature distribution in the modified laser ATP process with increased roller and mandrel temperatures and pre-heating of the substrate.

Figure 7 shows the temperature distribution for the modified process. It is clear that near the nip point, at least 2-3 layers of substrate are above the melting temperature. This could lead to improved consolidation and better mechanical properties.

7 Discussion

Even though the thermal model presented previously is in agreement with the previously reported results, it has certain limitations which need to be addressed to improve its accuracy.

In general, rule of mixtures has been experimentally found to give a good approximation of the thermal conductivity of composites. In most previous experimental measurements, the polymer matrix and fibres were heated simultaneously. Laser heating is different in that the wavelength of the laser irradiation is tuned to selectively heat up either the matrix or the fibres. As direct heating of the polymer matrix using lasers could lead to poor control over heating rates, resulting in matrix damage, some of the new laser systems use wavelengths that are mainly absorbed by carbon fibres, which then indirectly heat up the surrounding matrix [10]. In such a scenario, the fibre-matrix interfacial thermal resistance could become important. Shenogin et al.

[11] list various parameters affecting the thermal properties of composites, one of them being the interfacial thermal property. The interfacial thermal resistance represents a barrier to heat flow associated with the difference in the phonon spectra of two phases and possible weak contact at the interface. This leads to backscattering of thermal energy waves or phonons. As a consequence, in the presence of a normal thermal flux, a temperature drop develops at the interface. They note that the resistance to the heat flow posed by the fibre-matrix interface is responsible for the low thermal conductivity of composites. Very little information exists on thermal conductivity of composites, when heated by laser irradiation. Note that using the available conductivity values is acceptable for most of the processes involving larger processing times. However, in laser ATP, where the tape is irradiated for a very small time duration that depends on the process speed, the interfacial thermal resistance could play an important role in development of temperature gradients and hence, consolidation.

In addition, the incident laser energy can have a non-uniform profile as reported by Grove [2]. The present model uses uniform thermal energy input. This could significantly affect the temperature distribution. The existing thermal model can be improved by taking measurements of contact length for the roller, the tape and the substrate, and the irradiation profile.

8 Conclusions

The potential of the Automated Tape Placement (ATP) process to replace the costly, and time-consuming autoclave process is well known. Recent developments of thermoplastic matrices with higher toughness and solvent resistance is attracting a renewed interest in this process. Laser ATP has been reported to offer high energy efficiency and superior dynamic control. The process has been investigated here numerically and experimentally. Thermal simulations of laser heating of the incoming prepreg tape and already laid substrate indicate that a very thin layer near the irradiation surface is heated to temperatures above the melting point of the thermoplastic PEEK matrix. This would limit the amount of consolidation. Experimental results (albeit with one set of process parameters only)

confirmed that the process does not lead to optimal bulk material properties, particularly those that depend on a high level of crystallinity. The ATP laminates exhibited a significantly weaker interlaminar bonding, in terms of ILSS and flexural strength but superior fracture toughness. Thermal simulations were also presented for possible process modifications using preheating and increased roller and mandrel temperatures, which lead to larger size of the melt pool. This could potentially facilitate a higher level of consolidation, bonding and crystallisation, giving stronger laminates. Finally, the inappropriateness of the available thermal conductivity values of composites for laser ATP modelling is highlighted.

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